

Core Outcome Set for Liver Transplant in Mitochondrial Neurogastrointestinal Encephalomyopathy (MNGIE): the COLT-MNGIE Project - Protocol

Authors: Rinaldi Rita¹, Baldin Elisa², Cescon Matteo³, Hirano Michio⁴, Malagelada Carolina⁵, Martí Ramon⁶, Massucci Serena⁷, Mattarozzi Katia⁸, Morelli Maria Cristina⁹, Pioli Silvano⁷, Roubertie Agathe¹⁰, Vignatelli Luca², Nonino Francesco²

¹IRCCS Istituto delle Scienze Neurologiche di Bologna, UOC Interaziendale Metropolitana (NeuroMet), Neurologia AOU S.Orsola-Malpighi, Bologna, Italy

²IRCCS Istituto delle Scienze Neurologiche di Bologna, Epidemiology and Biostatistics Unit, Bologna, Italy

³Department of General Surgery and Transplantation, IRCCS Azienda Ospedaliero-Universitaria di Bologna, Bologna, Italy

⁴Department of Neurology, Columbia University Irving Medical Center, New York, New York, USA

⁵Digestive System Research Unit, University Hospital Vall d'Hebrón, Barcelona, Spain

⁶Vall d'Hebron Research Institute, Centro de Investigación Biomédica en Red de Enfermedades Raras (CIBERER), Autonomous University of Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain

⁷Mitocon ONLUS, Rome, Italy

⁸School of Medicine - Department of Medical and Surgical Sciences (DIMEC), University of Bologna, Bologna, Italy

⁹Internal Medicine Unit for the Treatment of Severe Organ Failure, IRCCS Azienda Ospedaliero-Universitaria di Bologna, Bologna, Italy

¹⁰Departement de Neuropédiatrie, CHU Gui de Chauliac, Institut des Neurosciences de Montpellier, Montpellier, France

Abstract

Background - Mitochondrial neurogastrointestinal encephalomyopathy (MNGIE) is a very rare autosomal recessive disease leading to marked mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) maintenance abnormalities. Clinical manifestations include mainly intestinal (weight loss, cachexia, diarrhoea, intestinal pseudo-obstruction) and neurological (polineuropathy, ptosis, ophtalmoparesis, leukoencephalopathy) symptoms and signs. Due to its rarity and non-specific symptoms, MNGIE is often misdiagnosed. To correct the nucleoside imbalance responsible of mtDNA maintenance abnormalities, several therapeutic options are proposed, among which liver transplantation (LT). LT, like other permanent enzyme-replacement treatments for MNGIE, is a complex procedure and its efficacy should be clearly defined by outcomes that are relevant for patients and clinicians. Due to the extreme rarity of the condition, it is unlikely that evidence from controlled trials will ever be available; therefore, consistency in research methods on MNGIE is of pivotal importance, particularly in defining efficacy and safety outcomes. A core outcome set (COS) is therefore warranted to adopt consistent, clinically meaningful and useful effect measures for MNGIE.

Methods and findings – The COLT-MNGIE project is promoted by the MITOCON advocacy group for people affected by mitochondrial diseases. COS will be developed according to the Core Outcome Measures in Effectiveness Trials (COMET) Initiative standards and recommendations by means of a mixed method approach including scoping literature review, focus groups and semi-structured interviews with key informants (people with MNGIE and carers/family members) and a modified Delphi method adapted from the COMET approach to select, score and summarise the outcomes. Each outcome will be described by

adopting unambiguous outcome descriptors. Dissemination and implementation strategies will be developed.

Conclusions - A core outcome set will be developed in MNGIE by means of a rigorous methodology, allowing the consistent evaluation of the efficacy and safety of LT and other promising permanent enzyme-replacement treatments for MNGIE.

BACKGROUND

Mitochondrial neurogastrointestinal encephalomyopathy (MNGIE) is an autosomal recessive disease caused by mutations in the thymidine phosphorylase gene (TYMP) leading to a marked reduction or absence of thymidine phosphorylase (TP), with subsequent systemic toxic accumulation of nucleotides thymidine (dThd) and deoxyuridine (dUrd), causing mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) maintenance abnormalities, especially in nervous and gastrointestinal tissues. MNGIE is a very rare condition involving severe gastrointestinal and neurological symptoms that are often misdiagnosed. A consensus conference held in 2019 produced evidence-based statements on MNGIE, leading to a consensus on the diagnosis, natural course, prognostic factors and available treatments of MNGIE (Hirano 2021).

Currently no disease-modifying treatment with proven efficacy is available and the course of the condition is invariably fatal. Nevertheless, several experimental therapeutic approaches, aimed at permanently replace the enzymes are under research. Among those, liver transplantation (LT) has shown promising results (De Giorgio 2016, Kripps 2020, D'Angelo 2020).

Compared to other alternatives, such as allogeneic hematopoietic stem cell transplant (AHSCT) (Halter 2015), LT has the advantage of providing permanent enzyme replacement with a potentially better safety profile. Moreover, a split liver transplant can be performed from a living donor (Kripps 2020).

LT is a complex procedure involving multidisciplinary approach and its efficacy should be clearly defined by outcomes that are relevant for patients and clinicians. Due to the extreme rarity of the condition, the results available from clinical studies addressing the efficacy of potential treatments are usually based on small case series (Halter 2015, Kripps 2020, D'Angelo 2020) and it is unlikely that evidence from adequately powered controlled trials will ever be available. Therefore, consistency in research methods on MNGIE is of pivotal importance, particularly in defining the outcomes adopted by researchers to assess the efficacy of therapeutic interventions. They should be meaningful for patients and consistently measurable with quantitative methods by clinicians, allowing their pooling to detect effect estimates that may not be appreciable in small samples.

Scope: A Core Outcome Set (COS) represents the minimum that should be measured in a clinical trial for a particular condition (Gargon 2014). The aim of the COLT-MNGIE project is to develop a COS to be used in research on the efficacy, safety and value of LT for MNGIE. Such outcome set may be valuable to assess also

other permanent enzyme-replacement treatments (PERT), such as haematopoietic stem cell transplantation (HSCT).

Any stage of the condition will be considered in order to implement a common definition of improvement or worsening shared with patients. Such outcome measures will allow measuring relevant clinical aspects of the treatment of MNGIE with LT and other therapeutic strategies, incorporating health and wellbeing dimensions that are relevant for people affected by MNGIE. The COS will be a useful tool to implement in future clinical trials in order to improve the quality, consistency and therefore usefulness of research in MNGIE. Potential barriers to the implementation of the COS will be addressed during its development.

METHODS

COS will be developed according to the Core Outcome Measures in Effectiveness Trials (COMET) Initiative standards and recommendations (Kirkham 2017, Williamson 2017).

Stakeholders involved

Healthcare professionals (neurologists, paediatric neurologists, gastroenterologists, transplant surgeons, post-surgical ICU specialists, nutritionists), biochemists and other researchers/professionals, persons with MNGIE, their care givers and methodologists.

The COLT-MNGIE project is promoted by MITOCON, *Insieme per lo studio e la cura delle malattie mitocondriali Odv*, the Italian advocacy group on mitochondrial diseases.

A Scientific Advisory Group (SAG) will be nominated, including clinicians with expertise in MNGIE (in neurology, gastroenterology, transplant surgery, neuropediatrics), a biochemist, a methodologist, a person with MNGIE and a representative of the advocacy group promoter (MITOCON).

Clinicians who participated in the previous Consensus Conference on MNGIE (Hirano 2021) and all healthcare professionals involved in the management of MNGIE will be invited to participate in this project. Persons with MNGIE will be involved through the Italian, European and extra-European mitochondrial patient associations, and informed about the scope, methods and development stages of the COLT-MNGIE project.

Information sources

A preliminary list of outcomes will be identified through a scoping literature review. Outcomes relevant for people with MNGIE will be identified through semi-structured interviews submitted by MITOCON staff to a global sample of people with MNGIE and their carers/family members. The structure and content of the interviews will be informed by focus groups supervised and tutored by an experienced psychologist. The number of interviews will be determined by achievement of saturation point and categorized in a list of Patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs).

Clinical and instrumental outcomes will be defined by reaching consensus among a multidisciplinary expert panel during a set of Delphi rounds (see below).

Outcomes will be organized into categories (referring to the diagnostic or therapeutic process, or to a clinical event) and domains. Timing of assessment and measurement tool and technique will be specified for each outcome.

Consensus process

The development of the COS will be achieved according to two procedures: one for PROMs and one for clinical and instrumental outcomes.

PROMs

A global sample of people with MNGIE and their carers/family members will be interviewed via video conference by the MITOCON international network staff to identify meaningful outcomes related to their health status. Themes to be assessed in the semi-structured interviews will be identified by means of a focus group involving a sample of people with MNGIE. PROMs identified will be ranked according to their importance through a scoring system. Interviewed participants will be asked to score each of the PROMs proposed by means of a scale of 1 to 9 (1 to 3 'not important', 4 to 6 'important but not critical' and 7 to 9 'critical'). The mean of the scores will be calculated and the PROMs scoring in the range of "important" or "critical" levels will be included in the final COS. Each outcome will be described in plain language by adopting clear and unambiguous health outcome descriptors (Baldeh 2020). Written consent to be interviewed will be obtained from informants.

Clinical and instrumental outcomes

A scoring process and consensus definition among healthcare professionals will be performed by means of a modified Delphi method (2 rounds), adapted from the COMET approach, involving clinical content experts (neurologist, paediatric neurologist, gastroenterologist, transplant surgeon, post-surgical ICU specialist, nutritionist, rehabilitation specialist).

During the first Delphi round participants will be provided with a list of outcomes developed through a scoping review of the biomedical literature and asked to score each of the outcomes listed using the GRADE scale of 1 to 9 (1 to 3 'not important', 4 to 6 'important but not critical' and 7 to 9 'critical').

An option to add additional outcomes that they think are relevant together with a score for each outcome added will be offered.

For the purpose of this project, consensus is defined as agreement of a substantial majority (75% or greater) of experts according to one of the above reported categories (not important, important but not critical, critical). The items assigned to the important or critical importance groups by at least 75% of the

participants will be included in the final list. The items considered of low importance by at least 75% of the participants will be excluded. The rest of the items will be brought forward to the second round.

During the second Delphi round the list of outcomes neither included nor excluded in the first round and the new proposed items will be considered. Each participant will be presented with their score from round 1, asked to consider responses from the other members of their stakeholder group, asked to re-score the outcome (changes to scores will be documented) by means of the abovementioned GRADE scoring scale. The same voting and prioritization procedures as in first round then will follow, producing a new list, inclusive of outcomes that passed both phases of the Delphi process.

The possibility for a third Delphi round will be considered based on the results of the first two rounds.

Analysis

The development of the COS and the feedback to the participants is planned through the structured interviews, the two online voting rounds previously described and two TC meetings.

The first TC meeting will involve the SAG and will include: introduction and sharing of the project’s aims, methods, workflow and timeline; presentation of a conflict of interest management policy.

The final meeting will involve the SAG, all the content experts who participated to the Delphi rounds and representatives of the MITOCON network. During the final meeting the results of the qualitative structured interviews with persons with MNGIE (list of PROMs) and of the Delphi survey (list of clinical and instrumental outcomes) will be presented and discussed. The distribution of scores, for each outcome and a summary of the results concerning outcomes from the structured qualitative interviews and the Delphi rounds will be shared with the stakeholders. Participants will be given in advance both outcome lists.

Dissemination strategies will be proposed and agreed upon.

Figure - COLT MNGIE: COS project plan

Ethics and Dissemination

A dissemination plan of the COS will be agreed within the SAG and shared for discussion with the group of stakeholders during the final meeting.

Namely, participants will be asked to discuss the editorial policy in relation to the publication of the COS on peer-reviewed journals, electronic platforms and social media, and a strategy to present the COS to healthcare professionals within scientific societies and associations, to patients, families and carers through advocacy groups, and to health care decisional settings (ministries of health, health care decision makers at national and local level).

Administrative information (Interest disclosure, funding)

All participants will be asked to sign a confidentiality agreement until the publication of the COS and to disclose interests that could potentially interfere with the main aim of the project by filling and signing specific forms. Disclosures will be available for all members and will be publicly accessible upon request.

The protocol will not be submitted to the local ethical committee, given that no individual clinical data will be shared or analysed and results from the semi-structured interviews will be anonymous.

The COLT-MNGIE project received no funding.

This protocol has been developed according to the COS-STAP statement (Kirkahm et al 2019) and the outcome set will be reported according to the COS-STAR standards (Kirkham et al 2016).

The protocol will be registered on Zenodo and on the COMET protocol database.

References

- Baldehy 2020** - Baldeh T, Saz-Parkinson Z, Muti P, Santesso N, Morgano GP, Wiercioch W, Nieuwlaat R, Gräwingholt A, Broeders M, Duffy S, Hofvind S, Nyström L, Ioannidou-Mouzaka L, Warman S, McGarrigle H, Knox S, Fitzpatrick P, Rossi PG, Quinn C, Borisch B, Lebeau A, de Wolf C, Langendam M, Piggott T, Giordano L, van Landsveld-Verhoeven C, Bernier J, Rabe P, Schünemann HJ. Development and use of health outcome descriptors: a guideline development case study. *Health Qual Life Outcomes*. 2020 Jun 5;18(1):167. doi: 10.1186/s12955-020-01338-8.
- De Giorgio 2016** - De Giorgio R, Pironi L, Rinaldi R, et al. (2016) Liver transplantation for mitochondrial neurogastrointestinal encephalomyopathy. *Ann Neurol*;80:448-455.
- D'Angelo 2020** - D'Angelo R, Boschetti E, Amore G, et al. (2020) Liver transplantation in mitochondrial neurogastrointestinal encephalomyopathy (MNGIE): clinical long-term follow-up and pathogenic implications. *J Neurol* ;267(12):3702-3710. doi:10.1007/s00415-020-10051-x.
- Gargon 2014** - Gargon E, Williamson PR, Altman DG, Blazeby JM, Clarke M. The COMET Initiative database: progress and activities from 2011 to 2013. *Trials*. 2014 Jul 10;15:279. doi: 10.1186/1745-6215-15-279
- Halter 2015** - Halter JP, Michael W, Schupbach M, et al. (2015) Allogeneic haematopoietic stem cell transplantation for mitochondrial neurogastrointestinal encephalomyopathy. *Brain*;138:2847-2858.
- Hirano 2021** - Hirano M, Carelli V, De Giorgio R, et al. (2021) Mitochondrial neurogastrointestinal encephalomyopathy (MNGIE): Position paper on diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment by the MNGIE International Network. *J Inher Metab Dis* ;44(2):376-387. doi:10.1002/jimd.12300.
- Kirkham 2016** - Kirkham JJ, Gorst S, Altman DG, Blazeby JM, Clarke M, Devane D, Gargon E, Moher D, Schmitt J, Tugwell P, Tunis S, Williamson PR. Core Outcome Set-STANDards for Reporting: The COS-STAR Statement. *PLoS Med*. 2016 Oct 18;13(10):e1002148. doi: 10.1371/journal.pmed.1002148.
- Kirkham 2017** - Kirkham JJ, Davis K, Altman DG, Blazeby JM, Clarke M, Tunis S, Williamson PR. Core Outcome Set-STANDards for Development: The COS-STAD recommendations. *PLoS Med*. 2017 Nov 16;14(11):e1002447. doi: 10.1371/journal.pmed.1002447. PMID: 29145404; PMCID: PMC5689835.
- Kirkham 2019** - Kirkham JJ, Gorst S, Altman DG, Blazeby JM, Clarke M, Tunis S, Williamson PR; COS-STAP Group (2019) Core Outcome Set-STANDARDISED Protocol Items: the COS-STAP Statement. *Trials*. 11;20(1):116. doi: 10.1186/s13063-019-3230-x. PMID: 30744706; PMCID: PMC6371434.
- Kripps 2020** - Kripps KA, Nakayuenyongsuk W, Shayota BJ (2020) Successful liver transplantation in mitochondrial neurogastrointestinal encephalomyopathy (MNGIE). *Mol Genet Metab*;130:58-64. doi: 10.1016/j.ymgme.2020.03.001.
- Williamson 2017** - Williamson PR, Altman DG, Bagley H, Barnes KL, Blazeby JM, Brookes ST, Clarke M, Gargon E, Gorst S, Harman N, Kirkham JJ, McNair A, Prinsen CAC, Schmitt J, Terwee CB, Young B. The COMET Handbook: version 1.0. *Trials*. 2017 Jun 20;18(Suppl 3):280. doi: 10.1186/s13063-017-1978-4.